

It has been observed that the substitution of OH, NO₂ and NH₂ group in benzoic acid increases the conductivity of benzoic acid progressively. The effect of NH₂ group is more than NO₂ group, which is more than OH group for the solutions in methyl, propyl and butyl alcohols and acetone. Similar results have been obtained for the molecular conductivities of these acids in ethyl alcohol by Hunt and Briscoe (*loc. cit.*).

Conductivity of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid in methyl alcohol and acetone is more than that of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid solutions in these two solvents. Results have been explained by Briscoe and Hunt on the basis of the electronic theory of valence and current theories of molecular structure.

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A NOTE ON THE ISOLATION OF SAKURANIN, A GLUCOSIDE FROM THE BARK OF *PRUNUS PUDDUM* (N. O. ROSACEAE)

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The stem bark of *Prunus Puddum* has been shown in this laboratory to contain a flavone, Puddumetin, which has been shown to be identical with Genkwanin (7-methoxy-5:4'-dihydroxyflavone; Chakravarti and Ghose, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 171), a flavone, Sakuranetin (7-methoxy-5:4'-dihydroxyflavone; Chakravarti, Kundu and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1948, 25, 329) and an isoflavone, which has been named Prunusetin (Chakravarti and Bhar, *ibid.*, 1945, 22, 301).

Though this work is being continued in this laboratory for more than five years, recently Narasimhachari and Seshadri (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 30, A, 271) have published a paper in this line and hence it is necessary to put on record our observations.

The note describes the isolation of another component from the bark of *Prunus Puddum*, the glucoside Sakuranin, which was isolated by Asahina, Shinoda and Inubuse

(*J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1927, 550, 133 ; 1928, 553, 29) from the bark of *Prunus Pseudo Cerasus* and the most noteworthy observation is that the specimen of the bark from which the glucoside has been isolated contains only traces of the other components, e. g. Puddumetin, Sakuranetin and Prunusetin. Probably the chemical composition of the bark is dependent on the seasonal variation or it might be possible that the different components are present in different layers of the bark, as it has been observed that the glucoside occurs particularly in the immature bark of trees which are not very old.

A trace of another glucoside has also been isolated and it is being further investigated.

Isolation of the Glucoside from the bark of Prunus Puddum.—The powdered bark (2400 g., in 4 lots) was extracted with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus, and each lot was extracted with about one and a half litres of ether for 16 to 18 hours.

The ethereal extract, which was orange-yellow in colour, was filtered, and the ether was completely removed by distillation. The residue was obtained as a reddish brown gelatinous mass. The gelatinous mass was repeatedly (3-4 times) treated with about 50 c. c. of cold benzene, with which it was thoroughly mixed, and the supernatant clear benzene layer decanted off. The residue was then dried in vacuum and the dried mass dissolved in the minimum amount of boiling absolute alcohol, after which the solution was allowed to stand for about a week, but no crystals separated. The alcohol was completely removed and the pasty mass was refluxed with small amounts of dry benzene for several times (4-5 times). The pasty residue was then dissolved in the minimum amount of boiling absolute alcohol and the solution on standing for several days deposited a solid, which could not, however, be collected by filtration on account of the presence of much slimy matter in the mother-liquor.

The supernatant alcoholic mother-liquor was decanted off very carefully and the solid was washed with anhydrous benzene and the wash benzene was decanted into mother-liquor, when a pasty mass was precipitated. By repeated treatment with absolute alcohol and washing with benzene, a solid was obtained which crystallised from absolute alcohol as needles, m. p. 213-14°.

The yield of the glucoside is roughly 0.05% of the weight of the dried bark. It is soluble in water, ethyl alcohol, sparingly soluble in ether and insoluble in benzene. (Found in sample dried in vacuum at 130-140° for 8 hours : C, 58.88 ; H, 5.38. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{24}O_{10}$: C, 58.86 ; H, 5.36 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Glucoside : Isolation of Sakuranetin and Glucose.—The glucoside (1 g.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (5%, 40 c. c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solution was filtered and the residue crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) and from benzene, m. p. 150-51° (mixed melting point with the sample of sakuranetin isolated from the bark of *Prunus Puddum* in this laboratory). (Found : C, 66.8 ; H, 4.8 ; OMe, 10.90. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$: C, 67.0, H, 4.9 ; OMe, 10.8 per cent).

Sakuranetin monomethyl ether (m.p. 116-117°) and sakuranetin oxime (m.p. 201-203°), prepared from this sample were identical in all respects with the derivatives of an authentic sample of sakuranetin.

The filtrate after hydrolysis gave on treatment with phenylhydrazine acetate, as usual, glucosazone (m.p. 205-206°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of glucosazone).

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A NOTE ON PERIODATES OF CADMIUM

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The following periodates of cadmium are reported in literature :

1. Secondary cadmium mesoperiodate, CdHIO_5 .
2. Cadmium metaperiodate, $\text{Cd}(\text{IO}_3)_2$.
3. Trihydrated cadmium diparaperiodate, $\text{Cd}_4 \text{I}_2 \text{O}_{11}, 3\text{H}_2 \text{O}$.
4. Pantahydrated cadmium mesoperiodate, $\text{Cd}_3 (\text{IO}_5)_2, 5\text{H}_2 \text{O}$.
5. Ennehydrated cadmium dimesoperiodate, $\text{Cd}_2 \text{I}_2 \text{O}_9, 9\text{H}_2 \text{O}$.

Out of the five periodates of cadmium only two were found to be formed, viz., secondary cadmium mesoperiodate, CdHIO_5 , and hexahydrated cadmium mesoperiodate, $\text{Cd}_3 (\text{IO}_5)_2, 6\text{H}_2 \text{O}$, as described below.

Secondary cadmium mesoperiodate, CdHIO_5 , was prepared by adding an excess of a hot solution of periodic acid to a warm suspension of cadmium carbonate in water. The excess of the acid was ensured by litmus paper. The mixture was stirred and kept hot till there was no effervescence. A fine gelatinous precipitate was formed which turned granular on standing. It was filtered, washed with water till free from the acid and then dried at 60° in a hot air-oven. It was analysed as follows.

The cadmium content of the periodate was determined by the pyridine method (Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis," 1946, p. 510).

The percentage of iodine in the periodate was found by Kimmins' method as modified by Bahl and Partington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1088).